

Structural equation model of academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, engagement and secondary school students' performance in economics in south-west, Nigeria

Banjo Moshood Lawal ¹

¹Unicaf University, Larnaca, Cyprus

Abstract

This study examined structural equation model of academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, engagement and secondary school students' performance in economics in south-west, Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. A sample of 1.125 senior secondary school II economics students was drawn out of a population of 362.834 from public and private schools in South-west, Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was used to select three states (Ogun, Oyo, and Ekiti), and the respondents involved in the study. Standardized instruments were used for data collection with reliability indices of .78, .79, .76, .75, and .75 for academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement, and performance in economics respectively. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and path analysis at .05 level of significance. The study revealed that the data on academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and performance in Economics fitted the hypothesized model ($\chi^2=126.27$; $df=43$; $\chi^2/df=2.94$; $p\leq.05$); and that there was significant causal relationship among academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and students' performance in Economics ($R=.55$; $p\leq.05$); and that the relative contribution of academic mindset and academic perseverance were significant ($R=.55$; $\beta=.41$; $\beta=.15$; $p\leq.05$). The study concluded that academic mindset and academic perseverance were strong predictors of secondary school students' performance in economics in south-west, Nigeria. The study recommended that education stakeholders should do their best to ensure that they cultivate a positive academic mindset and academic perseverance in students of economics.

Keywords: Non-cognitive variables; structural equation model; performance; economics; students

INTRODUCTION

Learning is an instinct of living creatures and has always been an issue of great concern for parents, school administrative bodies, educational policymakers, and students. Learning or latent variable, typically measured as academic performance in continuous assessment and end of term examinations is shaped by a wide variety of factors intrinsic to students and their external environment. In students' performance, the place of mindset, motivation, perseverance, social skills, engagement, self-regulation, self-discipline, and learning strategies cannot be overemphasized (Jason et al., 2012). As observed by Pike et al. (2003), academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, and engagement are positively related to academic performance. This suggests that in addition to content knowledge and academic skills, individual students must develop sets of behaviors, skills, attitudes, and strategies that are crucial to academic performance.

Economics is one of the school subjects commonly chosen as a course of study. As a subject, it is concerned with the study of scarce resources allocation to satisfy unlimited wants, and it is in the light of this that Yusuf (2014) viewed it as an integral part of human life. For economics to be meaningfully learned by students, non-cognitive variables must be harnessed. Harnessing these variables could bring about meaningful learning and enhanced academic performance. However, the extent to which students' performance in economics could be enhanced depends on certain non-cognitive variables such as academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, and academic engagement. The learning capability of a well-taught student with reasonable level of these variables might be geared up thereby leading to improved academic performance of the student in economics.

Corresponding Author

Banjo Moshood Lawal, Unicaf University Old International Airport, 7130 Larnaca, Cyprus,
E-mail: b.lawal@unicaf.org

Received : 6 November 2023

Accepted : 5 December 2023

Online Published : 29 December 2023

©2023 JSER, Available online at
<https://www.journalser.com>

Cite this article as: Lawal, B. M. (2023). Structural equation model of academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, engagement and secondary school students' performance in economics in south-west, Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 2(2), 85-93. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444314>

One of the variables capable of dictating students' academic performance in economics is academic mindset. Academic mindsets are the psycho-social attitudes or beliefs one has about oneself in relation to academic activities both at home and in school (Farrington et al., 2012). Students' academic mindset affects the quality, duration, and intensity of their engagement in academic behaviors (attending class & studying) and adopts learning strategies that, in the end, can powerfully affect students' learning and academic performance either positively or negatively (Jason et al., 2012). A number of studies have been undertaken on academic mindset at various levels of education. Most of these studies support the notion that academic mindset is a strong facilitator of academic performance and that a positive or negative change in the concept tends to produce a commensurate change in academic performance (Valentine et al., 2004; Yara, 2010). Feeling part of a school or classroom environment will make students more likely to engage in productive academic behaviors. Dweck (2008) found a positive correlation between academic mindset and students' academic performance. Factors capable of dictating students' performance cannot be exhaustively discussed without reference to academic perseverance.

Perseverance is the ability to stick with the same point of view as the previous one after negative influences, resistance, or discouragement (in spite of obstacles). It involves dealing with hurdles rationally rather than complaining (to efficiently move further in accomplishing a task instead of being irritated about the task). In the academic milieu, academic perseverance means the degree to which a student could continue engaging in academic activities in spite of difficulties or obstacles within or outside the academic environment (Okunbanjo, 2014). In relation to academics, De-Vera et al. (2015) posit that perseverance is related to better performance and greater success not only in academia but also in the real-world setting. It is believed that students who persevere tend to work harder and longer and are more inclined to engage in voluntary practices so as to enhance academic performance or success. Empirically, Mattern (2005) found in his study that students who have perseverance skills and the capability to achieve their goals are able to get more chances and face academic challenges; which will consequently lead to good academic performance. They have the best learning skills, positive attitude towards their academic skills, have a higher passion of love and explore new ideas. Duckworth et al. (2007) and found the academic perseverance of psychology undergraduates to be significantly correlated with academic performance. On the contrary, the result disagreed with that of Bazelais et al. (2016) who found that there was no significant relationship between perseverance and students' academic achievement.

Another variable of interest in this study is academic engagement. Academic engagement is a set of behaviors that signal serious psychological investment students devote to educational activities inside and outside of the classroom setting. In the opinion of Akin (2009), students' academic engagement is the extent to which they are actively involved in significant educational experiences and activities. The definition above factored out two things that are highly salient to student engagement, which are active involvement, and

significant educational experiences. In its simple form, academic engagement is a construct that describes behaviors usually related to being a good student. These, according to Farrington et al. (2012), include frequently attending class, arriving ready to work (with necessary learning materials), paying attention, taking part in instructional activities and class discussions, and devoting out-of-school time to studying and completing homework. Academic engagement encompasses components like behavioural, emotional and cognitive characteristics of students (Fredricks et al., 2004). Academic engagement cannot be exhaustively discussed without reference to academic motivation. Finlay (2006) found that students' engagement factors have no statistically significant correlations with academic performance. Similarly, Hayam-Jonas (2016) found that there was no relationship between engagement and academic achievement. However, Pearce (2014) found a significantly positive correlation between the level of academic engagement and academic achievement in students' high school mathematics.

Academic motivation as a variable has also been explored by scholars such as Ryan and Deci (2000), Omondi (2005) and Slavin (2006). Academic motivation is the energetic force behind students' inspiration to learn and excel in academic work. The place of motivation in academic success cannot be jettisoned because it is what gets one going, keeps one going, and determines where one is to go (Slavin, 2006). Motivation is one of the elements that contribute to academic performance. It is crucial to a student's academic success at any age and any academic level. This is on the notion that development of academic motivation has significant implications for academic careers either in the short run or at the long run. Academic motivation is an imperative concept in academic settings and is linked to increased levels of academic performance. Students with high level of academic motivation are more probable to have increased levels of academic achievement. Atieh et al. (2016) found a non-significant relationship between academic motivation and academic performance. On the contrary, Othman and Leng (2011) reported among others that there was a significant positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement.

In recent times, the academic performances of students in their academic pursuit had not been encouraging. When examinations are conducted, students are expected to perform well but reverse is the case in most instances especially in external examinations like the West African Senior Secondary Examination (WASSCE). This assertion is evident in the trends of performance in the result released by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) from 2010 to 2017, in which the percentage of those that got credit or above was 56.25%, 59.50%, 56.09%, 66.94%, 51.22%, 46.61%, 44.7%, and 47.2% respectively. These, however, are not good enough considering the fact that social sciences students need at least credit in the subject to gain admission into a university in Nigeria. Among the conditions or factors affecting academic performance, the place of non-cognitive variables cannot be left out.

To simultaneously look into how non-cognitive variables influence students' performance in economics, there is need for

sophisticated analytical tools like structural equation model. structural equation models (SEM) is a statistical method used in testing hypotheses about the relationships among observed and latent (unobserved) variables. Structural equation models comprise both a measurement model for each latent variable and a structural model. According to Werner (2010), SEM as a statistical technique subsumes elements of traditional multivariate models, such as regression analysis, factor analysis and simultaneous equation modeling; and thus, is applicable in cases of latent variables that are not observed directly and in cases of intervening variables that have the role of the dependent and independent variable at the same time.

The result of SEM is often pictorially represented in the form of a diagram. This is useful for displaying the pattern of causal relations among a set of variables, which may ordinarily not be possible without the use of SEM. To achieve this, a model must be hypothesized and tested using the data collected on the variables of the study. The purpose of testing the model is to ensure the data collected fits the model. The indices that indicate fitness of a model as specified by Hooper, Coughlan and Mullen (2008) are Root Mean Square error of Approximation (RMSEA), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), and Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI). The RMSEA ranges from 0 to 1, with smaller values indicating a better model fit. A value of .06 or less is indicative of an acceptable model fit. The GFI and AGFI range between 0 and 1, with a value of over .90 generally indicating an acceptable model fit (Hooper et al., 2008). Similarly, Garson (2011) prescribed that, in determining a parsimonious model, paths with beta coefficients that are less than 0.05 should be considered statistically insignificant and therefore be deleted, while beta coefficients up to 0.05 but not significant could be retained on the basis of meaningfulness.

Based on the principles of SEM, the researcher, therefore, hypothesized a structural model of selected non-cognitive variables and secondary school students' performance in Economics in South-west, Nigeria. This was done to fill some

of the research gaps observed in the area of entrepreneurship education and employment creation.

The purpose of this study

The major purpose of this study was to examine structural equation model of academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, engagement and secondary school students' performance in Economics in South-west, Nigeria. In line with the statement of the problem and purpose of the study, the following research questions were raised and answered in the course of the study.

- To what extent do academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and performance in Economics fit the hypothesized structural equation model?
- What is the more parsimonious causal model for explaining students' performance in Economics given academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, and engagement?
- Is there significant causal relationship between academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, and academic engagement with students' performance in Economics?
- What is the significant relative contribution of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance and academic engagement to the prediction of secondary school students' performance in Economics?

METHOD

This study adopted ex-post facto research design. This design was considered appropriate because it allows the use of correlations among already existing variables in assessing the theoretical propositions about the variables. On the basis of the ex-post facto design, the researcher hypothesized a structural equation model (SEM) diagram in an attempt to examine the cause-effect relationship. The model was based on the outcomes of empirical studies reviewed in this report. In doing so, causal thinking plays an important role in the application of SEM analysis. The hypothesized model incorporated three types of variables: (a) exogenous variables, which include

Figure 1: Hypothesized structural equation model of selected non-cognitive variables and students' performance in economics

academic mindset ($X1$) and academic motivation ($X2$) that were not influenced by other variables in the model; (b) mediator variables, which are academic perseverance ($X3$), and academic engagement ($X4$); and (c) endogenous variable – students' performance in economics ($X5$) as being predicted by the other variables. In the model, direct influence of the antecedent variables on the criterion variable (performance in economics) were proposed. This is shown by the arrows that lead from $X1$ and $X2$ to $X5$. Also, indirect effects were conjectured that show how $X1$ and $X2$ relates to $X5$ through the moderator variables of academic perseverance $X3$ and academic engagement $X4$. The model is presented Figure 1.

KEY:

$X1$ = Academic Mindset (AM)

$X2$ = Academic Motivation (AMO)

$X3$ = Academic Perseverance (AP)

$X4$ = academic engagement (AE)

$X5$ = Performance in Economics (PE)

The population of this study comprised all the Senior Secondary School Students in South-west zone of Nigeria. South-west of Nigeria has six states, namely Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti. The target population for the study was all Economics students in Senior Secondary Two (SS 2) in all the schools across the six states in the geopolitical zone with a total enrolment of 362.834 students. Simple random sampling technique was used to select three states (Ogun, Oyo and Ekiti) out of the six states in South-west zone of Nigeria. Also, simple random sampling was used to select 45 senior secondary schools and 1125 Senior Secondary School II Economics Students for the study. Standardized Academic Mindset Scale, Academic Perseverance Scale, Academic Engagement Scale, Academic Motivation Scale, and Economics Performance Test were used for data collection. All the instruments were adapted for the purpose of this study. Reliability coefficients of the scales stood at 0.78, 0.79, 0.76, 0.75, and 0.75 for academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement, and Economics performance test respectively. Descriptive statistics was used in describing the demographic profile of the respondents in the form of frequency and percentage. Path analysis and percentage were used to answer research question d. Furthermore, path analysis was used to answer research questions a, b and c. at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The analysis started with the correlation matrix of the variables in the study as shown in Table 2 to ascertain the absence of multicollinearity.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of the Variables in the Study

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. Academic Mindset	-			
2. Academic Motivation	0.34*	-		
3. Academic Perseverance	0.25*	0.49*	-	
4. Academic Engagement	0.45*	0.27*	0.13*	-
5. Performance in Economics	0.63*	0.12*	0.26*	0.35*

Note. * $p < .05$

Results in Table 2 show the inter-correlations among the variables in the study. It can be inferred from the analysis that there was no any evidence of multicollinearity among the variables. To prove absence of multicollinearity, Pallant (2003) is of the opinion that the observed correlation must not exceed 0.70; as correlation coefficient above that value signifies the presence of multicollinearity and this may jeopardize the forecasting power of the upstream variables on the downstream variable. The highest correlation coefficient among the variables is 0.63; which is the relationship between academic mindset and performance in Economics. This meant that none of the correlation coefficient of the variables exceeds 0.70. In other word, there is absence of multicollinearity among the variables in the study.

Research Question One: To what extent do academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and performance in Economics fit the hypothesized structural equation model?

To answer the research question, the fitness indices of the ratio of Chi-square to the degree of freedom (χ^2/df), Goodness-of-fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI), Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), as specified by Usluel et al. (2008), were evaluated. The information is presented in Figure 2.

The fitness indices and other information regarding Figure 2 are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary Statistics for Fitness of the Tested Model

Fit Index	Recommended Value	Observed Value
Chi-square/degrees of freedom (126.27/43)	≤ 3.0	2.94
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.97
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
RMSEA	≤ 0.06	0.04

GFI = goodness-of-fit index; AGFI = adjusted goodness-of-fit index; NFI = normed/normal fit index; CFI = comparative fit index; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation

The ratio of Chi-square (χ^2) to its degrees of freedom (df) was 2.94 and was within the acceptable range of ≤ 3.0 . Also, as specified by Hooper et al. (2008), the other goodness-of-fit indices were within the acceptable ranges which indicated a good fit. Thus, to a great extent, the sampled data fitted the hypothesized model because all the fitness indices were within the acceptable range. However, despite the fact that the model fit the sample data, certain causal paths were not significant in the model. The path from academic perseverance to academic engagement and the path from academic motivation to academic

Figure 2: Structural Equation Model of Selected Non-cognitive Variables and Students' Performance in Economics

Performance were not significant (see Figure 2). As such, there is a need for model trimming in order to arrive at a more parsimonious model.

Research Question Two: What is the more parsimonious causal model for explaining students' performance in economics given academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance and engagement?

To answer the research question, path trimming was done to delete certain paths with coefficients that are not statistically significant and/or are not meaningful in the explanation of the model in Figure 2. As prescribed by Garson (2011), paths with beta coefficients which are less than 0.05 should be considered statistically insignificant and therefore be deleted, while beta coefficients up to 0.05 but not significant could be retained on the basis of meaningfulness. The more meaningful causal model is presented in Figure 3.

The fitness indices and other information regarding Figure 3 are presented in Table 4.

Having deleted the causal path from academic perseverance to academic engagement and the causal path from academic

motivation to academic performance that were not significant nor meaningful, all the path coefficients retained in the output model in Figure 3 are more than 0.05, therefore no path should be deleted again in the output diagram which means that all paths in the model are important. As specified by Hooper et al. (2008), the other goodness-of-fit indices were within the acceptable ranges which indicated a good fit. As such, the more parsimonious causal model that explained the performance of students in economics is the model with three direct and four indirect paths whose path weights were significant and meaningful.

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Fitness of the More Parsimonious Model

Fit Index	Recommended Value	Observed Value
Chi-square/degrees of freedom (127.73/45)	≤ 3.0	2.84
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.97
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.98
RMSEA	≤ 0.06	0.04

GFI = goodness-of-fit index; AGFI = adjusted goodness-of-fit index; NFI = normed/normal fit index; CFI = comparative fit index; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation

Figure 3: More Parsimonious Structural Equation Model of Selected Non-cognitive Variables and Students' Performance in Economics

Research Question Three: There is no significant causal relationship of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance and academic engagement with students’ performance in Economics.

To answer the research question, joint causal relationship (R-value) and the R² value of the causal relationship among academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and students’ performance in Economics were extracted from SEM analysis and the tested hypothesized model in Figure 3. The causal relationship is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Causal Relationship Results

R	R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	p-value
0.55	0.30	5.64	0.001

Results in Table 5 show that there is causal relationship among academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and students’ performance in economics with the correlation (R) value of 0.55 which is significant at p-value of 0.001. Furthermore, the R-square value of 0.30, as contained in the table, means that the independent variables of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, and academic engagement jointly predicted students’ performance in Economics by 30%; which, therefore, means that 70% of variations in students’ performance in Economics is accounted for by variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Four: There is no significant relative contribution of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance and academic engagement to the prediction of secondary school students’ performance in economics.

To answer the research question, the unstandardized estimates, standardized estimates, standard errors, and t-values of the variables in the study were extracted from SEM analysis and the tested hypothesized model in Figure 3. Path coefficient in SEM and factor loading in factor analysis are equivalent to regression coefficients. The standardized coefficients are used in this study to determine the relative contribution because they are transformations of unstandardized estimates that remove scaling information and can be used for comparisons of parameters of the model. The result is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Relative Contributions of Academic Mindset, Academic Motivation, Academic Perseverance, and Academic Engagement to Students’ Performance in Economics

Variables	(B)	SE	(β)	t-values	p-values
Mindset	3.450	.443	.41	7.79	.001
Motivation	–	–	–	–	–
Perseverance	.949	.208	.15	4.57	.001
Engagement	.728	.489	.09	1.49	.13

Results in Table 6 show the contribution of each of the independent variables to the model. It reveals that academic mindset contributed Beta weight of .41 and the t-value of 7.79 which is significant at .001. Furthermore, academic perseverance contributed Beta weight of .15 and the t-value of 4.57 which is significant at .001. Academic engagement contributed Beta weight of .09 and t-value of 1.49 and it is not

significant to students’ performance in economics at .13. However, all the variables, except academic motivation, contributed to students’ performance in economic, but only the contribution of academic mindset and academic perseverance were significant. This means that they had direct effects on students’ performance in economics.

DISCUSSION

The first finding of the study revealed that academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and performance in economics greatly fitted the hypothesized model with chi-square (χ^2) value of 127.73, df = 45, and χ^2/df ($127.73/45$) = 2.84. This revealed that the chi-square value and other fitness indices evaluated in the study were within the acceptable ranges which were indicative of good model fit. This result might be due to the fact that the data collected conformed to assumptions of multivariate normal distribution, number of required indicators and model identification as specified by Kaplan (2007) that structural equation model (SEM) programs required an adequate number of known correlations or covariances as inputs in order to generate a sensible set of results and to achieve this, the model must be over identified (the number of data set must be more than the specified correlations). This result was, therefore, in line with the acceptable model fitness indices as specified by Hooper et al. (2008) that for a model to be considered fit, the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) and Normed/Normal Fit Index (NFI) must be greater than 0.90 and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) should be below 0.06.

The second finding showed that the more parsimonious causal model that explained performance of students in economics was the model with three direct and four indirect paths whose path weights were significant and meaningful. This result was possible where the path weights of the causal links in the parsimonious model were within the acceptable values for significance and meaningfulness. This result corroborated Garson (2011)’s specification that paths with beta coefficient up to 0.05 could be retained on the basis of significance and meaningfulness, as well as had a link with the dependent variable (criterion). In the more parsimonious mode, 85.5% of the total effects were direct while 14.5% were indirect; which was an indication that academic mindset, academic perseverance and academic engagement exerted direct influence on academic performance more than indirect influence.

This discussion could not be considered complete without reference to the causal relationship among academic mindset, motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and students’ performance in economics. The result obtained showed that there was significant causal relationship among academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and students’ performance in economics. This meant that the independent variables of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, and academic engagement highly correlated with students’ performance in economics. This result was plausible

where the independent variables played important roles in students' academic performance, especially in economics. This result was in line with the earlier work of Pike et al. (2003) who reported that non-cognitive variables of academic mindset, motivation, perseverance, and engagement positively related to academic performance. This result was also consistent with the findings of Farrington et al. (2012) who reported that student's mindset determined the motive behind his action, the extent to which he persisted at school work; which in turn would manifest itself through better academic behaviors (engagement) and consequently led to improved academic performance.

The results further revealed that though there was a significant relative contribution of academic mindset and academic perseverance to the prediction of students' performance in economics but there was no significant relative contribution of academic motivation and academic engagement to students' performance in economics. This meant that academic mindset and academic perseverance had direct influence on students' performance in Economics. This result was plausible where the sampled respondents had positive mindset and positive spirit of perseverance towards academic activities; which consequently led to high academic performance in economics. The observed significant direct influence/contribution of academic mindset corroborated the work of Affum-Osei et al. (2014) who investigated the relationship between academic mindset and academic performance of high school students and found a significant correlation between academic mindset and academic performance. With respect to academic perseverance, the observed significant contribution corroborated the findings of Duckworth et al. (2007) and found academic perseverance of psychology undergraduates to be significantly correlated with academic performance.

It was also revealed that the relative contribution of academic motivation to performance in economics was not significant. This meant that students' academic motivation and performance in economics did not move in the same direction capable of yielding a significant relationship. This result is possible where motivation did not exert direct influence on academic performance, but rather work jointly with other variables to influence academic performance especially in Economics. This result corroborated the earlier work of Atieh et al. (2016) who found a non-significant relationship between academic motivation and academic performance. However, this result negates that of Othman and Leng (2011) who reported among others that there was significant positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement.

An issue of interest in the study was that the results revealed that the relative contribution of academic engagement to performance in economics was not significant. This meant that academic engagement was not a predictor of performance in economics. This result is in line with that of Hayam-Jonas (2016) who found that there was no relationship between engagement and academic achievement. This result refuted the findings of Pearce (2014) who found a significantly positive correlation between the level of academic engagement and academic achievement in students' high school mathematics.

Limitations

The limitations of the study are listed as follows:

- i. The study was limited to South-west zone of Nigeria in which the sample size was from only three states. If the study had covered the whole zones, it might have had a different finding in terms of generalizability.
- ii. The study considered only 4 selected variables (i.e. academic mindset, academic perseverance, academic engagement and academic motivation) amongst countless variables capable of predicting secondary school students' performance in economics. The mode of the results might possibly be different had more variables been considered.

Not minding these limitations, the researcher still considered the result valid at least in the area of the study. As such, these observed limitations did not, in any way, render the results and the conclusions drawn from the study invalid; since the study was empirically carried out and analyzed with relevant statistical methods. The results might, therefore, be adjudged valid and reliable for generalization purposes. The study might also be found useful to future researchers in the areas of structural equations especially in Economics. Using the results and discussion might be of assistance to school administrators, teachers and parents to gain a clearer insight of the kind of variables needed to be encouraged if their students must achieve better academic performance.

Conclusion

Having discussed the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that academic mindset and academic perseverance, if empirically handled and analyzed, could be strong predictors of students' academic performance in Economics. However, academic motivation and academic engagement though had been reported as important contributor variables but, in this study, their contributions to academic performance were not significant. The influence of academic motivation and academic engagement on performance in economics still remains controversial and deserves in deep empirical research.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and their educational implications already highlighted, it was hereby recommended that education stakeholders should do their utmost best to ensure that students have a positive mindset about their academics and imbibed spirit of perseverance in academic activities since the variables had been confirmed to have causal relationship with academic performance in economics. Furthermore, the confirmation of the variables of academic mindset and academic perseverance as having causal effects on student's academic performance in economics should be of significant consideration in academic discussion.

Finally, it was further recommended that measurement and evaluators as part of stakeholders in the education sector, be alive to the intertwined causal relationship among academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance, academic engagement and academic performance and their role

in unraveling the influence of academic mindset, academic motivation, academic perseverance and academic engagement in schools.

Funding: The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest exists for this manuscript for any of the authors.

Availability of Data and Material: Data will be available on request.

Ethical Approval: The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its following updates.

Consent to Participate: Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

REFERENCES

- Adebule, S. O. (2004). Gender differences on a locally standardized anxiety rating scale in mathematics for Nigerian secondary schools in Nigerian. *Journal of Counselling and Applied Psychology, 1*, 22-29.
- Adegoke, B. A. & Ajadi, T. A. (2016). Structural modeling of teacher characteristics, skills in teaching, and students' achievement in secondary school physics. *Journal of Studies in Education, 6*(2), 81-94. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jse.v6i2.8932>
- Affum-osei, E., Eric, A. A., Barnie, J. & Forkuoh, K. S. (2014). Achievement motivation, academic self-concept and academic achievement among high school students. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science, 2*, 24-37.
- Akin, S. (2009). What does the community college survey of Student engagement (CCSSE) have to do with learning? *Community College Journal of Research and Practice, 33*(8), 615-617. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10668920902915181>
- Atieh, M., Hasan, S., Fezzeh, N. A., Mohammad, K. & Hoda, E. (2016). The relationship between academic motivation and academic performance among students at Mazandaran University of medical sciences. *International Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies, 1*, 1419-1426.
- Bazalais, P., Lemay, D. J. & Doleck, T. (2016). How does grit impact college students' academic achievement in science? *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education, 4*(1), 33-34. <https://doi.org/10.30935/scimath/9451>
- De-Vera, M. J., Gavino Jr, J. C., & Portugal, E. J. (2015). *Grit and superior work performance in an Asian context*. Proceedings of 11th International Business and Social Science Research Conference, January 2015, Crowne Plaza Hotel, Dubai.
- Duckworth, A. L., Peterson, C., Matthews, M. D., & Kelly, D. R. (2007). Grit: Perseverance and passion for long-term goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 92*(6), 1087-1101. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.92.6.1087>
- Dweck, C. S. (2008). *Mindsets and math/science achievement. Paper prepared for the Carnegie-IAS Commission on Mathematics and Science education*. Retrieved from <http://opportunityequation.org/teaching---and---leadership/mindsets---math---science---achievement>.
- Farrington, C. A., Roderick, M., Allensworth, E., Nagaoka, J., Keyes, T. S., Johnson, D. & Beechum, N. O. (2012). *Teaching adolescents to become learners: The role of non-cognitive factors in shaping school performance*. Chicago: University of Chicago Consortium on Chicago School Research.
- Finlay, K. A. (2006). *Quantifying school engagement*. Research report National Center for School Engagement. Denver, CO: NCSE.
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. & Paris, A.H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research, 74*, 59-109. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543074001059>
- Garson, D. G. (2011). Testing Statistical Assumptions, in: Blue Book Series, Ashe-boro.
- Hayam-Jonas, A. (2016). *The relationship between student engagement and academic achievement*. Doctoral Thesis, University of Auckland.
- Hooper, D., Coughlan, J. & Mullen, M. (2008). Structural equation modeling: Guidelines for determining model fit. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods, 6*(1), 53-60.
- Jason, S., Cheri, F. & Ginger, S. (2012). Students' academic mindset interventions: A review of the current landscape. *Impaq International Foundation, 1*, 1-54.
- Kaplan, D. (2007). *Developments in multilevel structural equation modeling*. Presented to the German institute for international educational research, Frankfurt, Germany.
- Mattern, R. A. (2005). College students' goal orientations and achievement. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, 17*(1), 27-32.
- Okunbanjo, A. O. (2014). Academic perseverance and class attendance as correlates of students' academic engagement among secondary school students in Ogun state. *European Journal of Educational Sciences, 1*(2), 133-140.
- Omondi, N. O. (2005). *Relationship between achievement motivation and performance in English composition writing among secondary school students in Nyando District, Kenya*. Unpublished Master of Education Thesis, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Othman, N., & Leng, B. K. (2011). The relationship between self-concept, intrinsic motivation, self-determination and academic achievement among Chinese primary school students. *International Journal of Psychological Studies, 3*(1), 233-241. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijps.v3n1p90>
- Pallant, J. (2003). *SPSS Survival Manual: A Step by Step Guide to Data Analysis Using SPSS for Windows (Versions 10 & 11)*. Open University Press: Philadelphia.

- Pearce, A. (2014). *Academic Engagement and Achievement in High School Mathematics*. Thesis Vancouver Island University.
- Pike, G. R., Kuh, G. D & Gonyea, R. M (2003). The relationship between institutional mission and students involvement and educational outcomes. *Research in Higher Education*, 44(2) 241-261. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022055829783>
- Ryan, R. & Deci, E. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54-67. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1999.1020>
- Slavin, D. (2006). *The Educational Psychology: Theory into Practice*. Prentice Hall.
- Valentine, J. C., DuBois, D. L., & Cooper, H. (2004). The relations between self-beliefs and academic achievement: A systematic review. *Educational Psychologist*, 39, 111-133. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep3902_3
- Werner, W. (2010). *Introduction to structural equation modeling course notes*. Retrieved on from <http://www.smallwaters.com/weblinks>
- Yara, P. O. (2010). Students' self-concept and mathematics achievement in some secondary schools in southwestern Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(1), 127-132.
- Yusuf, S. A. (2014). *Informal Sector and Employment Generation in Nigeria*. Online at <http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/55538/>.